

1 ***Taming the Space: Semantic Modelling***
2 ***using Linked Open Data of Fuzzy Wobbling***
3 ***Geospatial Data from the Archaeological***
4 ***and Geosciences domains***

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20 **ABSTRACT**

21 Archaeological and geoscientific research often relies on spatial data whose
22 precision and reliability vary considerably. Coordinates derived from excavation
23 reports, literature, or modern surveys frequently embody vagueness, ambiguity, or
24 conflicting interpretations. This paper addresses such wobbling geospatial data by
25 presenting a semantic approach that embeds uncertainty directly into Linked Open
26 Data (LOD). At the core of this approach lies the Fuzzy Spatial Locations Ontology
27 (FSL-O), which builds on PROV-O, SKOS, and GeoSPARQL to model entities, activities,
28 and agents alongside explicit properties for certainty, provenance, and
29 methodological detail. Its implementation in the fuzzy-sl Wikibase extends this
30 framework through a dedicated schema for geolocation and coordinate metadata,
31 enabling the documentation of precision, methods, sources, and actors. The SPARQL
32 Unicorn Toolkit further supports visualisation by integrating these data into GIS
33 environments and generating human-readable HTML outputs. The methodology is
34 demonstrated through interdisciplinary case studies: Ogham stones with multiple
35 biographies between ancient findspots and museum contexts; Campanian Ignimbrite
36 deposits serving as Late Pleistocene chronological markers; poorly documented
37 numismatic hoards from Croton; and Roman Samian ware distributions. Each
38 example illustrates how uncertainty can be expressed as structured,
39 machine-readable information, rather than being hidden or oversimplified. By
40 embedding fuzziness into LOD, this work enhances the FAIRness, transparency, and
41 interoperability of archaeological and geoscientific datasets. It contributes to
42 international debates on how to responsibly represent spatial uncertainty and
43 provides a foundation for future extensions of ontology and Wikibase models across
44 broader cultural heritage and scientific domains.

45
46 **Keywords:** FAIR, Linked Open Data, uncertainty, Archaeology, Ogham, Samian Ware,
47 Geosciences, Campanian Ignimbrite, Wikibase

Introduction & Background

49 Archaeological and geoscientific research is deeply reliant on spatial data, yet the
 50 production and use of such data are rarely free from uncertainty [1], [2]. Coordinates
 51 derived from historical sources, excavation reports, field surveys, or secondary literature
 52 often contain vagueness, ambiguities, or imprecision that complicate their interpretation
 53 and reuse [3], [4], [5], [6]. This situation gives rise to what we refer to as “fuzzy wobbling
 54 geospatial data”, locations that shift depending on the source, method, or interpretative
 55 framework employed [7]. Unless such uncertainty is explicitly recorded, the resulting
 56 data cannot be considered transparent, reproducible, or reusable in the long term.

57

58 This challenge aligns directly with the FAIR Principles [8], now widely recognised as a
 59 cornerstone of modern research data management. Achieving FAIRness requires more
 60 than simply publishing datasets: the context of their creation, including the methods and
 61 assumptions underlying geospatial coordinates, must also be documented. For
 62 archaeological and geoscientific datasets, where site locations may be vague or
 63 disputed, this transparency is essential to ensure trust in the data and to enable
 64 meaningful reuse across disciplinary boundaries.

65

66 **Figure 1** - A distributed Knowledge Graph Scheme bringing together Linked Open
 67 Data and FAIR Digital Objects approaches. Florian Thiery & Andreas Noback, CC BY
 68 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons.

69 Linked Open Data (LOD) [9], [10], [11] offers a framework for addressing these
 70 requirements. By representing information in graph-based structures using standards
 71 such as RDF, SPARQL, and GeoSPARQL [12], [13], LOD allows heterogeneous datasets to
 72 be semantically connected and enriched. This approach has particular relevance for
 73 archaeology, a discipline that inherently integrates diverse forms of evidence, from
 74 geological stratigraphy and palaeoenvironmental records to artefact typologies and
 75 textual sources. LOD enables the integration of such evidence within the federated

76 interdisciplinary knowledge graph (FIKG, Fig. 1), while at the same time enabling the
77 explicit modelling of uncertainty and provenance.

78

79 The need for explicit modelling is especially evident when spatial information is
80 transferred between communities and infrastructures. Geoscientists may describe a
81 volcanic eruption layer in stratigraphic terms. At the same time, archaeologists may refer
82 to associated findspots, and historians may only mention the nearest settlement without
83 a shared semantic model that can capture the varying degrees of certainty, precision,
84 and spatial reference; such information risks remaining siloed, ambiguous, or even
85 misleading. By contrast, modelling uncertainty as part of the dataset itself enables a
86 richer and more honest representation of the past.

87

88 In recent years, several initiatives have highlighted the importance of documenting
89 vagueness and uncertainty in geospatial data, particularly through semantic
90 technologies. The adoption of ontology-driven approaches allows doubts and
91 imprecisions to be represented in a structured, machine-actionable way, rather than
92 being relegated to footnotes or omitted entirely. This ensures that subsequent users –
93 whether domain experts, interdisciplinary collaborators, or computational systems – can
94 interpret the confidence, methods, and limitations associated with each spatial
95 statement.

96

97 This paper builds on these developments by presenting a semantic modelling
98 approach for wobbling geospatial data. We focus on the Fuzzy Spatial Locations
99 Ontology (FSL-O), designed to capture vagueness, uncertainty, and provenance in
100 georeferenced data. Implemented within a federated ecosystem of Wikidata and
101 dedicated Wikibase instances, FSL-O provides a framework for integrating
102 archaeological and geoscientific datasets while making explicit the circumstances of
103 their creation. The paper further demonstrates how this model can be applied in practice
104 through a series of interdisciplinary case studies, ranging from early medieval Ogham
105 stones to Late Pleistocene volcanic deposits and ancient numismatic hoards.

106

107 By foregrounding uncertainty as an integral component of data modelling, our
108 approach seeks not only to enhance the FAIRness of archaeological and geoscientific
109 data but also to provide a methodological foundation for their long-term interoperability.
110 In doing so, we aim to contribute to a broader discussion within the CAA community on
111 how best to represent, integrate, and reuse spatial data that, by its very nature, continues
112 to wobble.

113

Methodology: SPARQL Unicorn & fuzzy-sl Ontology

114 The methodological core of this paper lies in the semantic modelling of vagueness
115 and uncertainty in geospatial data. While spatial coordinates are typically treated as
116 fixed and precise points in databases, archaeological and geoscientific practice reveals
117 a far more complex reality. Locations may be derived from excavation reports,
118 secondary literature, oral traditions, or modern field surveys, each with varying degrees
119 of precision and confidence. To make such variability transparent and reusable,

120 uncertainty itself must become part of the data model. In the following, we present the
 121 main tools and ontological frameworks that enable such modelling and visualisation: the
 122 SPARQL Unicorn Toolkit, the Fuzzy Spatial Locations Ontology (FSL-O), and the fuzzy-sl
 123 Wikibase.

124

125 **Figure 2** - Scheme of “fuzzy-sl” modelling, based on PROV-O, with the classes
 126 Entity, Activity and Agent. Florian Thier, CC BY 4.0.

127 The SPARQL Unicorn Toolkit [14], [15], [16], [17] provides the technical infrastructure
 128 for visualising Linked Open Data in GIS and for transforming machine-actionable RDF
 129 into human-readable outputs. Originally conceived as a broader FAIRification tool, in this
 130 paper, its role is restricted to two key functions: the integration of LOD into GIS
 131 environments such as QGIS and the generation of an LOD HTML documentation.
 132 Through its QGIS plugin, Linked Data queries can be performed directly against SPARQL
 133 endpoints, enabling the overlay of uncertain or fuzzy locations with other spatial
 134 datasets. For example, queries for Ogham stones, Campanian Ignimbrite findspots, or
 135 numismatic hoards can be executed and displayed as clustered layers in QGIS. The

136 same toolchain also enables the creation of HTML pages that render RDF triples in a
 137 navigable, human-readable form. In this way, the Unicorn Toolkit acts as an interface
 138 layer between the technical modelling of uncertainty and its use in everyday research
 139 practice.

140

141 **Figure 3** - fuzzy-sl Wikibase modelling scheme. Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0.

142 At the centre of this work, however, is the Fuzzy Spatial Locations Ontology (FSL-O), a
 143 semantic model specifically designed to capture what we refer to as “wobbling
 144 geospatial data.” FSL-O [18], [1] is built upon three established standards: PROV-O, SKOS,
 145 and GeoSPARQL (Fig. 2). Following the PROV-O concept [19], it distinguishes between
 146 *entities*, *activities*, and *agents*. A site is represented as an entity associated with a
 147 geometry, which is created by a method understood as an activity, and this activity is
 148 attributed to a person, the agent. This triadic structure ensures that every coordinate can
 149 be traced back to the procedure and authority by which it was produced. Crucially, FSL-O
 150 incorporates explicit properties to record uncertainty. Each site and its geometry can be
 151 described by two core attributes: *fsl:certaintyDesc*, a textual description of confidence or
 152 doubt, and *fsl:certaintyLevel*, a controlled vocabulary ranging from low to high, including
 153 dubious. Sites may further be linked to bibliographic references via *fsl:hasReference* or to
 154 online resources through *exactMatch* properties borrowed from the SKOS vocabulary.
 155 Methods, in turn, can be characterised through *fsl:hasSource* and *fsl:hasSourceType*,
 156 which identify the underlying data source and its category, *fsl:activityDesc*, which

157 documents the method in free text, and the already mentioned certainty properties,
 158 which carry over to the level of activities. Together, these properties allow not only the
 159 representation of where a site is located, but also the circumstances, evidence, and
 160 confidence with which this location has been established. The resulting RDF can then be
 161 transformed into HTML files through the SPARQL Unicorn Ontology Documentation
 162 research tool, ensuring that the ontology-driven data remains both machine-processable
 163 and accessible to human users.

164

165 **Figure 4** - Example Wikibase "fuzzy-si" modelling of Ai/Aii: Ogham Stone
 166 Coumeenole North (Q131) with current location (Ai) and finding site (Aii); B:
 167 Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot Auel Maar AU3 (Q70); C: Campanian Ignimbrite
 168 Findspot Urluia Quarry (Q73). Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0.

169 While FSL-O provides the conceptual framework, its integration into existing
 170 community infrastructures is essential. Wikidata, as one of the most widely used
 171 community-driven knowledge graphs, allows the modelling of spatial information via the
 172 property *P625* for geographic coordinates. However, such coordinates can be enriched
 173 with qualifiers and references to capture uncertainty. For instance, the modelling of an
 174 Ogham stone in Wikidata can distinguish between its ancient findspot and its modern
 175 exhibition location. Qualifiers such as determination method (*P459*), subject has role
 176 (*P2868*), and stated in (*P248*) enable the documentation of whether a coordinate was
 177 derived from georeferencing, obtained from a database entry, or observed on-site. The
 178 sourcing circumstances (*P1480*) qualifier can indicate whether the information was
 179 obtained through a direct survey. At the same time, location (*P276*) distinguishes
 180 between the different roles a place may play, such as a findspot, an exhibition venue, or a
 181 general reference. References to external resources, such as OpenStreetMap node
 182 identifiers (*P11693*), provide additional anchoring of the coordinate to collaborative
 183 geospatial repositories. By combining these qualifiers and references, a Wikidata item

184 can reflect both the ancient and modern biographies of a site, while making explicit the
185 methods and uncertainties associated with each location.

186

187 The most detailed implementation of the ontology-driven approach is achieved
188 through the fuzzy-sl Wikibase, a specialised Wikibase instance dedicated to modelling
189 uncertain geospatial data (Fig. 3). Its data model distinguishes between Geolocation
190 Metadata (GLM), represented as statements, and Coordinate Metadata (CM),
191 represented as qualifiers. GLM includes properties such as *relatedTo* (P10), which
192 connects a site to external resources in the LOD cloud; *hasReference* (P11), which
193 records a literature quotation or bibliographic source; *hasSpatialType* (P8), which
194 specifies categories like inhabited place, river, cave, maar, or supervolcano;
195 *hasSpatialCategory* (P26), which situates the location within domains such as geology or
196 archaeology; and *locatedInTheAdministrativeTerritorialEntity* (P32), which links to
197 corresponding Wikidata items for administrative units. These high-level statements
198 establish the basic context of a site. The current ten CM qualifiers then provide
199 fine-grained metadata about the coordinates themselves. *Precision* (P23) records the
200 number of significant decimal places in the WGS84 coordinate, thereby expressing the
201 numerical accuracy of the georeferencing (for example, $\pm 0.0001^\circ$ for the Franchthi
202 Cave). *CertaintyLevel* (P5) and *certaintyDescription* (P13) mirror the FSL-O properties,
203 allowing both a categorical and textual account of confidence. *MethodUsed* (P7) and
204 *methodDescription* (P15) document how the coordinate was obtained, whether by
205 external repository, literature-based georeferencing, or on-site survey. *ActingPerson* (P14)
206 identifies the individual responsible for the georeferencing activity, while
207 *sourceTypeGeneric* (P6) and *sourceTypeDetail* (P16) provide further differentiation of the
208 evidence base, distinguishing between textual descriptions, papers, or
209 community-contributed sources such as OpenStreetMap. Finally, *locationType* (P24)
210 specifies the functional category of the location – whether it is a findspot, eruption site,
211 or museum display – while *pointType* (P33) indicates the conceptual role of the
212 coordinate, such as a representative point, a place as a concept, or a natural place. By
213 combining GLM and CM, the fuzzy-sl Wikibase thus enables the explicit recording of
214 both the contextual and methodological dimensions of geospatial data (Fig. 4).

215

216 The interplay of these three tools—SPARQL Unicorn for visualisation, FSL-O for
217 conceptual modelling, and the fuzzy-sl Wikibase for implementation – creates a
218 workflow that renders geospatial uncertainty transparent, reusable, and interoperable.
219 Rather than presenting a fixed or oversimplified representation of the past, this approach
220 acknowledges the wobbling nature of spatial data. It provides the means to document,
221 visualise, and critically engage with it. The following case studies will demonstrate how
222 this methodology can be applied to diverse datasets, ranging from epigraphic
223 monuments and volcanic tephra layers to numismatic hoards and ceramic distributions.

224

Case Studies: Ogham, Campanian Ignimbrite & Samian Ware

225 The methodological approaches outlined above gain their full relevance only when
226 applied to concrete research data. In the following, we demonstrate how the modelling
227 of fuzzy and wobbling geospatial data can be put into practice across a selection of

228 interdisciplinary case studies. The examples highlight how FSL-O and the fuzzy-sl
 229 Wikibase allow for a transparent representation of uncertainty, how the SPARQL Unicorn
 230 Toolkit facilitates visualisation, and how Linked Open Data infrastructures enable
 231 integration across domains.

233 **Figure 5 - Geospatial modelling of Ogham Stone CIIC 81 / Q74 / GARES/1 [20] at**
 234 **UCC Stone Corridor, no. IV. Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0.**

235 One of the longest-running and most illustrative examples is the Linked Open Ogham
 236 project. Ogham stones, erected mainly between the fourth and seventh centuries CE in
 237 Ireland and parts of Britain, are among the earliest written monuments of the Irish
 238 language [21], [22], [23]. They provide not only linguistic evidence but also insights into
 239 kinship structures, territorial organisation, and cultural contacts. Many stones, however,
 240 have complex biographies: some remain in situ, others were moved into museums, and
 241 many are known only from antiquarian reports. The fuzziness of their spatial references
 242 is thus intrinsic. Using the fuzzy-sl Wikibase, Ogham stones can be modelled with
 243 coordinates (P4) enriched by qualifiers and references. For instance, the stone CIIC 81
 244 (Q74¹), initially found at Garranes in County Cork, is documented both in its ancient
 245 findspot and in its current location in the UCC Stone Corridor no. 4 (Fig. 5). The
 246 exhibition site respectively findspot can be qualified as P5: High / Low; P13: on-site
 247 survey at exhibition area / GARES/1 [20]; P7: on-site survey / Georeferencing; P14:
 248 Florian Thiery; P6: on-site survey / Textual Description; P16: on-site survey / Paper; P15:
 249 on-site survey at UCC Cork / found in old documents; P23: $\pm 0.0001^\circ$; P24: Exhibition Site
 250 / Findspot; P33: Exhibition / Location of a Place as a Concept. CIIC 81, respectively,
 251 GARES/1 is also referenced to other resources in the FIKG, such as Wikidata
 252 (Q130529871), Semantic Kompakkt (Q1262), FactGrid (Q10000294), OSM node
 253 11071361392, and SMR ID C0074-148----. This dual modelling captures the spatial
 254 biography of the stone and the different confidence levels associated with each
 255 coordinate. In practice, these statements can be queried via SPARQL and visualised in
 256 QGIS through the Unicorn plugin, which enables both density maps and individual
 257 feature exploration. The Ogham case demonstrates how doubt, movement, and

¹ cf. <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/entity/Q74> (all links last accessed 09.09.2025)

258 interpretation can be preserved as explicit, machine-readable knowledge, rather than
 259 hidden in the margins of catalogues.

260

261
 262

Figure 6 - Campanian Ignimbrite findspots. Florian Thiery / Fiona Schenk, CC BY 4.0.

263

264
 265

Figure 7 - Scheme for determining the Urluia CI site. Florian Thiery / Fiona Schenk, CC BY 4.0.

266 A second example comes from the geosciences, namely the distribution of
267 Campanian Ignimbrite deposits. The eruption of the Campanian Ignimbrite around
268 39,940 yr b2k \pm 150 [24] represents one of the most significant volcanic events in Europe
269 during the Late Pleistocene, with ash layers distributed across vast parts of the
270 continent [4] (Fig. 6). Such tephra horizons serve as necessary chronological markers in
271 both geology and archaeology, yet the locations where they have been identified are
272 often imprecise. Some sites, like the Franchthi Cave in Greece, the Crvena Stiljena Cave
273 in Montenegro, or the Toplitsa Cave in Bulgaria, can be georeferenced relatively precisely
274 based on modern surveys [25], [26], [27], [28]. Others, like the Urluia Quarry in Romania²
275 [29], [30], are only approximately described in the literature, with coordinates
276 reconstructed from textual descriptions and geological maps. In FSL-O, each of these
277 sites can be represented as an entity with a geometry, created by a method attributed to
278 a person. The coordinate of the Urluia site [5] (Fig. 7), for example, is linked to sources
279 such as Fitzsimmons and Hambach [29], described with `fsl:hasReference` and
280 `fsl:certaintyDesc` (“The Urluia (URL) LPS is located in an abandoned limestone quarry on
281 the limestone plateau of the Dobrogea” [30, p. 5]), marked with a certainty level of
282 medium, having a close match to GeoNames 664132 and OSM way 84975654, and the
283 coordinates POINT(27.9021 44.0947). By encoding these aspects, the model preserves
284 not only the location but also the uncertainty of its derivation. The Campanian Ignimbrite
285 case illustrates how vagueness in the geosciences can be documented in a way that is
286 compatible with archaeological data, enabling cross-domain queries and joint
287 interpretations.

288

289 **Figure 8** - Findspots from London in the fuzzy-sl Wikibase. Florian Thiery & Allard
290 W. Mees, CC BY 4.0.

291 A third case study originates from numismatics and concerns the silver coinage of
292 Croton in southern Italy. The coin hoards³ associated with this ancient colony, dating
293 from the sixth to third centuries BCE, present a particularly challenging dataset, as the
294 findspots are often poorly recorded. Some hoards are documented with relatively
295 precise coordinates, such as the Via Paternostro hoard in Crotona (Q46), while others
296 are described only in broad regional terms like “Calabria” or “southern Italy”. In the
297 fuzzy-sl Wikibase, this range of certainty can be captured explicitly. The hoard from San
298 Giorgio Ionico (Q13), for instance, can be modelled with a coordinate derived from

² cf. http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_52

³ cf. https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/croton-geo/Site_collection/index.html

299 modern literature and linked to an OpenStreetMap node, with a certainty level of
300 medium. The Fiume Esaro hoard (Q67), by contrast, can only be placed approximately
301 along a river section, with the qualifier `certaintyLevel` set to low and `certaintyDescription`
302 noting the speculative nature of the attribution. Such modelling acknowledges the limits
303 of our knowledge rather than imposing a false precision. In addition, links to related
304 entities in Wikidata and Nomisma.org allow integration into broader numismatic
305 datasets, while still making visible that many mints and hoards remain “uncertain.” By
306 applying FSL-O and the fuzzy-sl Wikibase, numismatic data becomes both interoperable
307 and transparent, opening new opportunities for comparative research even when the
308 underlying evidence is fragmentary.

309

310 The fourth example highlights Samian ware, also known as Terra Sigillata, a widely
311 distributed Roman ceramic. Samian Ware is central to chronological frameworks in
312 Roman archaeology, but their provenances and distributions often suffer from similar
313 uncertainties as inscriptions or hoards. The Samian Research Database provides an
314 extensive catalogue of findspots [31], [32], [33]. Yet, the coordinates are not always
315 precise (Fig. 8). Some sites, like those in Londinium (Q101) or Southwark (Q107), can be
316 located with high confidence and linked directly to excavation reports. Others are vague
317 and require interpretation, such as London (Londinium) / No. 1 Poultry (Q95) or
318 Southwark / London Bridge (Q108). In the fuzzy-sl Wikibase, these sites can be modelled
319 with CM qualifiers documenting the method of coordinate assignment, whether through
320 on-site survey or literature-based approximation. Certainty levels can thus be assigned
321 on a case-by-case basis, providing a nuanced picture of spatial reliability across the
322 dataset. Through SPARQL queries and visualisation in QGIS, the data can then be
323 compared with other LOD resources, revealing patterns of distribution and trade while
324 remaining honest about the uneven quality of spatial evidence.

325

326 Taken together, these case studies demonstrate the versatility of semantic modelling
327 for wobbling geospatial data across different domains. Whether dealing with early
328 medieval inscriptions, volcanic tephra layers, ancient coin hoards, or Roman ceramics,
329 the combination of FSL-O, Wikidata, and the fuzzy-sl Wikibase provides a coherent
330 framework for making uncertainty explicit. By treating uncertainty as data rather than
331 noise, this approach allows researchers to integrate diverse sources more responsibly,
332 laying the foundation for interdisciplinary analyses that recognise the inherent fuzziness
333 of the past.

334

Extending Fuzziness:

335

Archaeometallic and Ceramic Sites in Cultural Geographies

336 Building upon the preceding examples of Ogham inscriptions, volcanic deposits, coin
337 hoards, and Roman ceramics, the following case studies broaden the application of
338 fuzzy geospatial modelling to archaeometallic contexts, regional site corpora, and
339 cultural landscapes. Each illustrates a different manifestation of uncertainty in
340 archaeological data—ranging from legacy datasets shaped by historical naming
341 conventions, to spatial records of varying precision, and to probabilistic reconstructions
342 of settlement distributions. Together, they demonstrate how semantic provenance and

343 fuzziness-aware modelling can integrate heterogeneous archaeological information
344 while preserving its inherent uncertainties.

345

346 **Figure 9** - Geographic map with ROT and BOO indicated, also showing hypothetical
347 origins for ancestral stages of Uralic subfamilies, and a distribution of
348 contemporaneous archaeological cultures (adapted from Grünthal et al. [34]), as
349 well as sites with Eastern European Hunter-Gatherer (EEHG) and Eastern Siberian
350 Late Neolithic/Bronze Age (LNBA) individuals. Childebayeva, A., Fricke, F., Rohrlach,
351 A.B. et al., CC BY 4.0, via [35, Fig. 1]

352 The first example concerns archaeometallic sites and the challenges of working with
353 fragmented, multi-source datasets. The fragmented nature of archaeological data forces
354 us to use in many cases to use as many sources for this data as possible. Sometimes
355 we are lucky enough to receive exact up-to-date data, but more often than not, we have
356 to deal with legacy data from decades ago. The age of the data itself comes with a
357 whole array of problems by itself. In terms of geographical data from the north of
358 Eurasia this is mostly caused by historical processes, which happened since the data
359 was collected. Name changes of cities, regions and states have been a frequent
360 occurrence in this region since the end of the 19th century. These issues underline the
361 importance of contextual metadata and temporal provenance tracking. In the fuzzy-sl
362 Wikibase, such datasets can be annotated not only with coordinates but also with the
363 historical and linguistic transformations that affect their interpretability, allowing modern
364 analyses to link ancient metallurgical contexts to present-day geographic references
365 without erasing the traces of their documentary evolution (Fig. 9).

366

367 A second example draws on the compilation of archaeological sites in Brandenburg,
368 showing how heterogeneous data sources can be reconciled through explicit modelling
369 of spatial uncertainty. Archaeology is inherently a very spatial discipline. The mapping of
370 find spots/sites for the distribution of types of material culture is a long-established
371 tradition in the field [36]. Sites are being discovered in a multitude of ways, intentionally
372 and unintentionally, and therefore, the documentation of the geographical location of
373 this site is as varied, resulting in different certainties and uncertainties. In a typical
374 research project, the gathering of data from different sources leads to a colourful mix of
375 certain and uncertain located finds. The spatial information may be very general (“in the
376 district”), specific, but not reconstructable (“in the north-eastern corner of the field of

377 farmer Giles” – but nobody knows anymore who farmer Giles was, and where his field
 378 lay) or very precise (GPS-measured coordinates with an error of maybe only 2 m).
 379 Depending on the research question, the precision of the information is very important.
 380 Therefore, when digitising older records, care must be taken to specify the certainty of
 381 the spatial information. To help others contextualise the now very abstract numerical
 382 values describing the site location more precisely than it ever was (coordinates of the
 383 site), it should be recorded how the site was discovered, how precisely the location was
 384 given in the source that was digitised and how large the error deriving from digitisation
 385 could be. Three examples: A modern excavation report will add geocoordinates with
 386 high precision. These coordinates can be used, but noted that they only declare the
 387 central point of the polygon describing the dig site. A field walker might describe the
 388 area of their finds as an area spanning maybe about 500 × 500 m. The site can be
 389 located with a point, but the note should be added that this is only an approximation by
 390 ca 500 m. And if retrodigitalising old maps, there are two factors apart from the
 391 information on how the site was found and localised initially: How well could a map be
 392 georeferenced and how much real-world space the drawn symbol in the analogue map
 393 takes up – therefore giving an error inherent in the localisation by digitisation process.
 394 The Brandenburg example underscores how fuzzy geospatial frameworks allow such
 395 diverse uncertainties to be expressed in a consistent, machine-readable way. By
 396 documenting the precision, method, and discovery context for each coordinate, even
 397 older, heterogeneous datasets can be integrated without losing their epistemic nuances
 398 (Fig. 10).

399

400 **Figure 10** - Combined ceramics sites in Brandenburg: different sources for
 401 findspots. Sophie C. Schmidt, CC BY 4.0.

402 Finally, the embedding of uncertainty in Urnfield Culture landscapes illustrates the
 403 analytical impact of explicitly modelling spatial vagueness.

404 Locations of archaeological sites are often either digitised from the literature or
 405 based on digital information. Many records tend to include descriptive information that
 406 cannot be tied down to a precise coordinate, much less the actual extent of the site.

407 Creating a point at the perceived center of the location is common practice; however,
 408 studies have emphasised the risks of misleading interference and interpretation through
 409 ignoring positional uncertainty, e.g. [37]. Figure 11 exemplifies this based on a catalogue
 410 of Hessian Urnfield Culture sites from 1948 [38]; each site is accompanied by a polygon
 411 encompassing the uncertainty of location based on the catalogue description. Kernel
 412 density surfaces and hexagonal aggregations (5 km and 10 km) initially suggest precise
 413 spatial concentrations, but when densities are weighted by site-specific uncertainty
 414 polygons, apparent clusters shift or dissipate. Such effects are especially pronounced at
 415 smaller scales, where the assumed central position of a site within its uncertainty
 416 polygon can drastically distort density statistics, particularly if the true location lies
 417 closer to the polygon's edge. This example highlights the necessity of embedding
 418 uncertainty explicitly into spatial analyses in order to gain more robust representations
 419 of archaeological landscapes. Here, semantic encoding of uncertainty within the fuzzy-sl
 420 framework provides the formal structure to capture these variability measures and link
 421 them to their methodological origins, ensuring that spatial statistics remain transparent
 422 and reproducible.

From Points to Patterns: Archaeological Spatial Analysis
 A methodological progression incorporating uncertainty

423

424 **Figure 11** - Location uncertainty partially incorporates the administrative
 425 boundaries of Hesse, Germany [39]. Analysis performed in R [40] with relevant
 426 packages [41], [42], [43], [44], [45], [46], [47], [48]. C. M. G. Giroto, CC BY 4.0; sites:
 427 Müller-Karpe 1948 [38].

428 Across these archaeometallic, ceramic, and cultural-geographical examples, the
 429 explicit treatment of uncertainty emerges as a shared methodological necessity. Each
 430 case illustrates how the FSL-O ontology and its Wikibase implementation transform
 431 heterogeneous and historically layered datasets into semantically coherent,
 432 FAIR-compliant resources. Rather than treating vagueness as a weakness, the approach
 433 turns it into structured knowledge – bridging disciplinary practices and paving the way
 434 for the broader reflections in the following discussion.

Discussion & Outlook

436 The results presented in this paper demonstrate how semantic modelling can
437 transform the way archaeological and geoscientific datasets are documented,
438 compared, and integrated. The focus here has been less on introducing the general
439 problem of uncertainty – already well recognised in both fields—and more on showing
440 how Linked Open Data provides the methodological means to deal with it in a structured
441 and interoperable manner. By applying the Fuzzy Spatial Locations Ontology (FSL-O) and
442 implementing it in the fuzzy-sl Wikibase, combined with visualisation through the
443 SPARQL Unicorn Toolkit, we have highlighted a workflow that captures not only
444 coordinates but also their provenance, confidence, and context.

445

446 The key methodological contribution of this work lies in bringing together three
447 elements: first, a formal ontology (FSL-O) that expresses vagueness and fuzziness
448 through explicit properties such as certainty level, certainty description, and references
449 to sources; second, a Wikibase implementation that extends this model through a
450 detailed schema for geolocation and coordinate metadata, allowing users to record
451 precision, methods, and agents; and third, an integration pathway to community-driven
452 infrastructures like Wikidata and OpenStreetMap, where data can be connected across
453 disciplinary and linguistic boundaries. This combination moves beyond traditional
454 gazetteers or databases by embedding uncertainty directly into the data model rather
455 than treating it as an external annotation.

456

457 The case studies underline the value of this approach. Ogham stones exemplify the
458 complex biographies of archaeological monuments, as they shift between findspots and
459 museum contexts. Campanian Ignimbrite deposits demonstrate how geoscientific and
460 archaeological data can be integrated when their uncertainties are modelled explicitly.
461 Numismatic hoards from Croton highlight the varying granularity of spatial descriptions,
462 from precise urban locations to broad regional references. Samian sites illustrate how
463 even well-established research databases require careful treatment of coordinate quality
464 and precision. In all these cases, semantic modelling enables researchers to express
465 differences in confidence, to trace methods of data creation, and to connect to external
466 resources. The interoperability of these datasets is enhanced precisely because
467 uncertainty is preserved as structured information. The integration of the
468 archaeometallic, ceramic, and cultural-geographical case studies further illustrates how
469 the fuzzy-sl approach transcends disciplinary boundaries. By applying the same
470 semantic logic to data originating from metallurgy, regional archaeology, and landscape
471 research, these examples demonstrate that uncertainty is not confined to a single data
472 type or scale. Instead, it manifests as a universal property of archaeological evidence,
473 which can be formally represented and computationally analysed through shared
474 ontological structures. This reinforces the potential of the fuzzy-sl framework to act as a
475 methodological bridge between site-based documentation, regional synthesis, and
476 cross-domain data infrastructures.

477

478 What sets this paper apart methodologically is its emphasis on Linked Open Data as
479 the backbone of interoperability. The use of RDF, PROV-O, SKOS, and GeoSPARQL

480 ensures that the data produced can be queried, linked, and visualised across
481 infrastructures. The explicit inclusion of uncertainty into this semantic framework is
482 what makes it distinctive. Rather than offering certainty where there is none, the
483 approach allows data to remain honest about its limitations while still being reusable.
484 This is particularly important in international and interdisciplinary contexts, where
485 researchers from archaeology, history, and the geosciences must be able to evaluate not
486 only the data itself but also the degree of confidence attached to it.

487

488 Visualisation is another critical area for discussion. While modelling uncertainty
489 semantically provides the foundation, researchers also need intuitive ways to see and
490 interpret it. The use of bounding boxes, buffers, or hulls makes fuzziness visible in maps,
491 but these techniques require careful calibration. For example, buffers generated in
492 WGS84 coordinates risk producing distortions that are technically correct but visually
493 misleading. The SPARQL Unicorn Toolkit addresses part of this challenge by enabling
494 semantically annotated data to be pulled into GIS environments where such
495 visualisations can be tested, compared, and refined. In this sense, the toolkit provides
496 not just a display mechanism but also an experimental environment for developing
497 user-friendly representations of uncertain space.

498

499 Looking forward, the next steps involve extending the ontology and the Wikibase
500 schema in response to further case studies. While the current model already
501 incorporates ten key properties for coordinate metadata, additional attributes may be
502 needed to capture temporal vagueness, different types of spatial abstraction, or more
503 nuanced descriptions of methods. Applying the model to new datasets—such as
504 archaeometallurgical evidence, large-scale cultural landscapes, or additional ceramic
505 corpora—will help to identify such requirements. The modularity of FSL-O and the
506 flexibility of Wikibase make them well-suited for this iterative refinement.

507

508 Another avenue for development lies in alignment with international standards and
509 infrastructures. Mapping FSL-O to CIDOC CRM and its archaeological extensions, or
510 linking Wikibase data to global initiatives such as the European Collaborative Cloud for
511 Cultural Heritage (ECCCH), will ensure that fuzzy geospatial data can participate in wider
512 ecosystems. This is particularly important for long-term sustainability: only if data
513 models are compatible across infrastructures can they be maintained and reused at
514 scale.

515

516 In conclusion, the central contribution of this paper is methodological. By embedding
517 uncertainty into Linked Open Data through the combined use of FSL-O, fuzzy-sl Wikibase,
518 and SPARQL Unicorn visualisation, we have shown a concrete pathway for dealing with
519 wobbling geospatial data in archaeology and the geosciences. The approach is
520 internationally relevant, interdisciplinary by design, and scalable through alignment with
521 broader infrastructures. Future work will focus on expanding the ontology and property
522 sets, integrating further case studies, and refining visualisation strategies. In this way,
523 the model not only acknowledges the inherent fuzziness of spatial information but also
524 provides the tools to make it transparent, interoperable, and FAIR.

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